

Measurement and Improvement Path Analysis of High-Quality Development Level of Higher Education in Henan Province of China

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ARTICLE INFO

Online Publication:
11 July 2025

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KEYWORDS: Higher Education; Ntropy Weighted TOPSIS; Henan Province

ABSTRACT

Higher education, as the core carrier of knowledge production, technology transformation and personnel training, realizes the high-quality development of higher education in the new era, which not only provides a cornerstone for cultivating new quality productive forces, but also provides a guarantee for promoting the improvement of national scientific and technological innovation level. Based on the data of Henan Province from 2013 to 2022, an evaluation index system for the high-quality development level of higher education was constructed, and the entropy weighted TOPSIS method was used to measure its development level. The calculation results show that the high-quality development level of higher education in Henan Province gradually increased from 2013 to 2022, but there is still a large space for further progress. This paper further puts forward some countermeasures and suggestions to promote the high-quality development of higher education.

1. INTRODUCTION

Higher education, as a core component of the national innovation system and a key driver of regional economic and social development, is crucial for enhancing the country's overall competitiveness. It also serves as a critical indicator of a province's comprehensive strength and future potential. In the context of the rapid advancement of the new round of technological revolution and industrial transformation, and the increasing urgency of the state's demand for high-quality development, how to scientifically assess and effectively promote the transition of the higher education system from scale expansion to quality improvement has become a focal point of concern for governments at all levels, universities, and all sectors of society. The 2024 Government Work Report proposed accelerating the construction of national strategic talent forces, striving to cultivate more first-class scientific and technological leaders and innovative teams, improving mechanisms for identifying and nurturing outstanding innovative talents, building platforms for the cultivation of basic research talents, creating a team of outstanding engineers and highly skilled talents, and increasing support for young scientific and technological talents. High-quality development in higher education is a vital component of the country's high-quality development and a solid pillar of economic and social development. Promoting high-quality development in higher education is an intrinsic requirement

for the green and sustainable development of Chinese higher education in the new era, an objective requirement for comprehensively building a strong country in higher education, and a necessary choice that follows the laws of higher education development and talent growth. Henan Province, as one of China's major economic, population, and agricultural provinces, has made significant progress in higher education in recent years, with the scale of educational institutions continuously expanding and the ability to serve local economic and social development steadily increasing. However, compared with the more developed provinces in the east, Henan Province still has a gap in higher education in terms of resource allocation, discipline development, talent cultivation quality, scientific and technological innovation, and internationalization. It faces the urgent task of enhancing its connotation, optimizing its structure, and strengthening its core competitiveness. A thorough analysis of the current state of higher education in our province is crucial for accelerating the construction of national strategic talent resources.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Currently research on measuring and evaluating the high-quality development of higher education has achieved certain results. Scholars both domestically and internationally have explored the quality of higher education from various perspectives, primarily focusing on the following areas: 1.

Research on the concept and connotation of high-quality higher education. Scholars have defined the quality of higher education from different angles, proposing various quality perspectives, such as comprehensive quality, process quality, and outcome quality (Zhong Xiaomin, 2020; Liu Guorui, 2021; Huang Honglan, 2021; Lazic Zorica, 2021; Gupta Asha, 2021).2. Construction of evaluation index systems for the high-quality development of higher education. Researchers have developed multiple evaluation index systems for higher education quality based on different theories and methods, covering aspects such as educational investment, educational process, and educational output (Xu Yijun, 2024; Zhao Zhiqiang, 2023; Huang Rong, 2022).3. Research on measurement methods for the high-quality development of higher education. Scholars have used a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, such as Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA), Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP), Principal Component Analysis (PCA), Entropy Value Method, and Entropy Weight-TOPSIS Method, to further measure the development level of higher education quality (Zhai Hongjiang et al., 2024; Li Jiabin, Wang Fengxiao, 2023).

Table 2 Research on evaluation of high-quality development level of higher education

In summary, the existing literature has provided valuable academic references for this research topic, but there is still considerable room for further exploration and expansion: First, systematic thinking and methods to comprehensively understand and deeply explore the theoretical framework of high-quality development in higher education are still rare. While the academic community has reached a consensus on the theoretical essence of high-quality development in higher education, there is significant disagreement on the specific aspects that constitute this development, which requires further investigation. Second, the research on high-quality development in higher education lacks a systematic analytical framework. Third, most existing studies focus on overall and dynamic national-level research, while local studies are insufficient, especially in provinces with large populations like Henan Province, which deserves more attention.

3.RESEARCHMETHOD

In this paper, the entropy weighted TOPSIS method is used to measure the level of high-quality development of higher education. Based on the relevant studies, the specific evaluation index system is constructed as follows:

Primary indicators	Secondary indicators	Three levels of indicators	Attribute
Innovative development	Innovation input	Full-time Equivalent of R&D Personnel	+
		R&D Expenditure Intensity	+
		University R&D Expenditure	+
	Innovation progress	Number of University R&D Projects	+
Number of Academic		+	

Table 1 Research on measurement and evaluation of high-quality development level of higher education

4. Research on the pathways for the high-quality development of higher education. Researchers believe that the high-quality development of higher education should focus more on the all-round development of individuals and promote human progress (Lin Miaoyu & Wang Jianhua, 2022; Li Hailong, 2023). Additionally, scholars have explored the pathways for the high-quality development of higher education in China from the perspectives of private higher education and vocational education (Wang Xiaowu & Wang Yating, 2022; Xu Qiong, 2023; Huai Fule, 2022; Cai Wenbo, 2022; Bruce Mwiya, 2017; Markus Seyfried, 2018).

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	Innovation output	Papers published	
		Number of Patent Application and Authorizations	+
		Number of Industrial Standards Formulated	+
		Income from Patent Ownership Transfer and Licensing	+
Harmonious development	Regional Synergy	Per-student Expenditure on Higher Education within the Public Financial Budget	+
		Hierarchical level Structure Synergy	Number of Enrolled Postgraduate Students
	Number of Enrolled Undergraduate and Junior College Students		+
	Faculty-Resource Coordination	Student-Faculty Ratio in Universities	+
		Number of Teachers with Doctoral Degrees	+
	Green development	Information Construction	Number of Computers for Teaching
Number of Network Multimedia Classrooms			+
Ecological Sustainability		Per-student Area of Campus Green Space	+
		Per-student Area of Sports Venues	+

Open development	International Cooperation and Exchange	Number of Enrolled International Students	+
		Number of Projects of International Conference Exchange Activities	+
		Number of Papers from International Exchanges	+
		Number of Accepted International-level Projects	+
		Shared development	Inclusive Education
Number of Graduates from Non-degree Higher Education Training Programs	+		
Social Service Sharing	Actual Income from Patent Transfer		+

The specific calculation steps are as follows:

Step 1: Standardization of data, and the standardization formula is as follows:

forward pointer :

$$Y_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij} - \min x_{ij}}{\max x_{ij} - \min x_{ij}} \quad (1)$$

Y_{ij} is the comprehensive evaluation matrix after standardization, and $\max x_{ij}$ and $\min x_{ij}$ are the maximum value and minimum value of the j th evaluation index of x in the i -th year.

Step 2: The weighted entropy method is used to calculate the weighting formula as follows:

(1) Calculation of index proportion:

$$p_{ij} = x_{ij} / \sum_{i=1}^n x_{ij} \quad (2)$$

(2) Calculate the information entropy of each component according to the proportion:

$$e_j = -\frac{1}{\ln n} \sum_{i=1}^m p_{ij} \ln(p_{ij}) \quad (3)$$

(3) Calculate the difference coefficient of information:

$$d_j = 1 - e_j \quad (4)$$

(4) Calculate the weight of each index:

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$$w_j = d_j / \sum_{i=1}^n d_j \quad (5)$$

Step 3: To construct a weighted evaluation standardization decision matrix, multiply the unquantified standardized matrix $Y = (y_{ij})_{m \times n}$ with the weight vector $W = (w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4, \dots, w_n)$. This results in the weighted standardized matrix $R_{m \times n} = (r_{ij})_{m \times n}$, $r_{ij} = w_j \times (y_{ij})_{m \times n}$.

Step 4: The optimal solution and the worst solution of the evaluation index are calculated as follows:

Optimal solution vector:

$$F^+ = (f_1^+, f_2^+, \dots, f_n^+) \quad (6)$$

The worst solution vector:

$$F^- = (f_1^-, f_2^-, \dots, f_n^-) \quad (7)$$

$f_j^+ = \max(f_{ij}^+)$, $f_j^- = \min(f_{ij}^-)$, $i=1, 2, 3, \dots, m$, $j=1, 2, 3, \dots, n$.

Step 5: The Euclidean geometric distance between the weighted information decision matrix and the ideal solution and the negative ideal solution is calculated, and its formula is expressed as follows:

$$d_j^+ = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (f_j^+ - f_{ij}^+)^2} \quad (8) \quad d_j^- = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^m (f_j^- - f_{ij}^-)^2} \quad (9)$$

Step 6: The closeness D between each sample index data and the ideal solution is calculated, and the relative closeness is obtained to obtain the comprehensive evaluation value.

$$D = \frac{d_j^-}{d_j^+ + d_j^-} \quad (10)$$

$0 \leq D \leq 1$, and the larger D is, the better the effect is, and vice versa.

Data from 2013 to 2022 in Henan Province were selected, all sourced from the China Statistical Yearbook, China Science and Technology Statistical Yearbook, China Education Statistical Yearbook, China Education Expenditure Statistical Yearbook, and the official websites of the Henan Provincial (Municipal) Bureau of Statistics. Some data required independent calculation, and for a few years, data was missing, which was filled using interpolation methods.

4.RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Table 1 Evaluation index entropy value and weight

Index	e_j	d_j	w_j
x1	0.9349	0.0651	0.0163
x2	0.8317	0.1683	0.0421
x3	0.8496	0.1504	0.0376
x4	0.7961	0.2039	0.0509
x5	0.8576	0.1424	0.0356
x6	0.5363	0.4637	0.1159
x7	0.8277	0.1723	0.0431
x8	0.8192	0.1808	0.0452
x9	0.8354	0.1646	0.0411
x10	0.8742	0.1258	0.0314
x11	0.9080	0.0920	0.0230

x12	0.9013	0.0987	0.0247
x13	0.8589	0.1411	0.0353
x14	0.8589	0.1411	0.0227
x15	0.9353	0.0647	0.0162
x16	0.8050	0.1950	0.0487
x17	0.8645	0.1355	0.0339
x18	0.8645	0.1355	0.0556
x19	0.9077	0.0923	0.0231
x20	0.7801	0.2199	0.0549
x21	0.8649	0.1351	0.0338
x22	0.7476	0.2524	0.0631
x23	0.8582	0.1418	0.0354
x24	0.7176	0.2824	0.0706

Data source: calculated by stata

Table 2 shows the positive and negative ideal values, proximity and ranking

Year	D+	D-	C	Seq
2013	0.2177	0.0440	0.1681	10
2014	0.2096	0.0468	0.1825	9
2015	0.2064	0.0475	0.1869	8
2016	0.2027	0.0515	0.2025	7
2017	0.1792	0.0767	0.2997	6
2018	0.1673	0.0945	0.3610	5
2019	0.1539	0.1107	0.4184	4
2020	0.1406	0.1261	0.4729	3
2021	0.0892	0.1751	0.6624	2
2022	0.0683	0.2136	0.7576	1

Figure 3 Line graph of comprehensive score from 2011 to 2022

It was calculated using formulas (1)-(10) that the comprehensive index of high-quality development of higher education in Henan Province continued to grow from 0.1681 to 0.7576 from 2013 to 2022, with an average annual growth rate of 14.5%, which was improving overall, becoming a stage-based development characteristic of accelerating quality improvement. Among them, 2017 was a key turning point. Since then, Henan Province has achieved remarkable results in high-quality development of higher education in

high-quality education, which is closely related to the "Double First-Class" university construction policy implemented by the country and the relevant supporting education support policies in Henan Province. Driven by the policy, the intensity of resource investment has been significantly increased, and the contribution to the innovative development dimension has continued to expand, providing a strong impetus for the development of education.

In the Henan Province High-quality Development Evaluation Index System for Higher Education, the weights of each dimension vary significantly. Among them, the dimension of innovation and development has the highest weight, highlighting that scientific and technological innovation and achievement transformation have a core driving role in the high-quality development of higher education. Among the specific indicators, such as "R&D personnel at that time", the weight of R&D input and output indicators is relatively large; the weight of coordinated development dimension is second, and the weight of indicators such as "university teacher-student ratio" is prominent, indicating that the coordination of faculty allocation and hierarchy structure is of importance for the high-quality development of higher education; in comparison, the weight of green development, open development, and shared development is relatively low, which shows that there is still a lot of room for development in terms of ecological sustainability, openness and universal education of high-quality development of higher education.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the data of Henan Province from 2013 to 2022, an evaluation index system for the high-quality development level of higher education was constructed, and the entropy weighted TOPSIS method was used to measure its development level. The calculation results show that the high-quality development level of higher education in Henan Province gradually increased from 2013 to 2022, but there is still a large space for further progress. Therefore, the following suggestions are put forward:

(1) At the policy level, the scientific nature, foresight, and effectiveness of policies are crucial to ensure that they can stimulate the vitality of higher education institutions, guide the rational flow of educational resources, and promote the balance between educational equity and efficiency. Additionally, attention is given to how these policies can drive reforms in the higher education system, enhance the quality assurance system, and improve educational equity.

(2) Regarding the allocation and investment of educational resources, research will focus on how to allocate educational resources reasonably based on Henan Province's specific conditions, thereby enhancing the efficiency of educational investment. This includes the rational distribution of educational funds, the optimization of

educational infrastructure, the enhancement of educational informatization, and the rational allocation of teaching staff.

(3) Research on talent cultivation models will focus on innovating existing educational methods and curricula to improve the quality of talent development. This involves updating course content, reforming teaching methods, strengthening practical teaching, and cultivating students' comprehensive qualities.

(4) Research on discipline and major construction will focus on optimizing the layout of disciplines and strengthening major construction based on the socio-economic development needs of Henan Province and even the country. This includes supporting emerging and interdisciplinary fields, upgrading traditional disciplines, and fostering and developing distinctive majors. (5) Enhancing research and social service capabilities is a key aspect of high-quality higher education development. Through school-enterprise cooperation and the application of research outcomes, research results can be transformed into practical productivity, thereby enhancing educational quality and promoting scientific innovation. (6) Internationalization is crucial for enhancing the competitiveness of higher education in Henan Province. By introducing high-quality international educational resources, promoting international exchanges among teachers and students, and participating in international education programs, Henan Province can advance the internationalization of higher education. Through these comprehensive measures, Henan's higher education will achieve high-quality and sustainable development, making greater contributions to the economic and social development of the region and even the country.

Funding: Henan Province Philosophy and Social Science Education Strong Province Project "Research on Measurement and Improvement Path of High-quality Development of Higher Education in Henan Province" (2025JYQS0281)

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